

*Epistolary Literature as a Teaching Strategy:
Perceptions and Perspectives*

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Abstract

Keywords: epistolary literature, reading and writing skills, teaching of reading and writing, reading, writing.

This article presents the partial results of the research project titled 'Strengthening Literacy Competencies through Epistolary Literature in Secondary Education Students in the Municipality of Pasto, Nariño, Colombia.' The study utilized the application and triangulation of semi-structured interviews, focus groups, and participant observation conducted with teachers and students from educational institutions in Pasto. The primary objective was to analyze perceptions regarding the methodological and didactic benefits of epistolary literature and its impact on the development of literacy competencies.

The study employs a qualitative method of actor-based data triangulation (Moreira-Aguayo et al., 2022), facilitating a comprehensive analysis through deep interpretation and cross-referencing of the gathered information. Findings from the discussion indicate that, for teachers, the use of narrative and theoretical writing promotes the enhancement of pedagogical practices. Conversely, for students, the elements of epistolary literature assist in communicating ideas and expressing emotions and thoughts once the conceptual framework is established.

In conclusion, the study identified epistolary literature as a tool that significantly contributes to strengthening literacy competencies by fostering 'intimate creativity' and improving communicative skills. Furthermore, the results highlight methodological and didactic challenges that must be addressed when designing strategies based on this genre. Such strategies should aim to facilitate 'sensory reading' and 'emotional writing,' thereby reinforcing literacy proficiency and consolidating socio-emotional skills such as empathy and resilience.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this article is to share partial results from the research project titled "Strengthening Literacy Competencies through Epistolary Literature in High School Students in Pasto, Nariño, Colombia." This study considers the perceptions of both students and classroom teachers regarding epistolary literature as a strategy for teaching, reading, and textual production. Given the urgent need to promote conscious and meaningful reading and writing processes, those that transcend the classroom to impact students' life projects and socio-emotional skills, epistolary literature emerges as a didactic alternative. It fosters intimate communication, the interaction between subjectivity and intersubjectivity, and the integration of testimonial narrative typologies that bridge diverse realities with the young reader's present.

Pedagogical and didactic challenges concerning literacy suggest the incorporation of formats that promote multimodal reading (Farfán & Gutiérrez, 2022). This involves understanding the complementary relationship between writing and reading, which triggers a framework of emotions rooted in recognition and expression (Sontag, 2021), thereby facilitating processes of inquiry and self-recognition.

Amidst complex contemporary landscapes and the necessity of embedding socio-emotional education across curricular structures (Ensucho & Aguilar, 2022), effective and affective literacy processes serve as pathways for meaning-making. These processes are capable of promoting emotional intelligence based on self-knowledge, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills (Goleman, 2022), ultimately strengthening interaction and coexistence.

Viewing epistolary literature as a narrative typology that involves singular experiences and the interaction between the realities of the author and the reader, an empathetic and close relationship favors a holistic view of the subject. It establishes complementarity through the development of sensitive and contextualized reading processes. Nonetheless, implementing a methodology supported by epistolary literature requires a comprehensive recognition of educational contexts and their actors, considering their specific needs, expectations, and motivations (Machado-Pérez, 2022).

Epistolary literature establishes a proximity to emotionality; therefore, it promotes reading and writing through the provocation of the intimate and the personal (Berdot, 2022), moving toward narrative poetics. From the perspective of Juárez-López (2022), this narrative subgenre can be appreciated both on a singular level through personal missives and on a social level through the classical epistle. From a sociological standpoint, epistolary literature facilitates processes of liberation and historical recognition (Gonzales-De Garay, 2022), as well as biographical confrontation, considering specific testimonies from artists and writers (Echeverry-Fernández, 2022).

The characteristics, interpretative possibilities, and the impact of subjectivity inherent in epistolary textuality lead to an exploration of perceptions surrounding this narrative typology. This exploration is based on the testimonial references of high school students and teachers in the city of Pasto regarding their previous experiences, insights, interests, and motivations, with the aim of analyzing its didactic and methodological benefits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In alignment with the proposed objective, the actor information triangulation method was applied as part of a qualitative, exploratory, and descriptive research study conducted with high school students and teachers from three institutions in the municipality of Pasto. Triangulation is positioned as a research alternative that enables

discourse analysis (Solórzano-Soto, 2022) and combines various techniques and instruments to obtain information and perceptions, thereby identifying points of convergence and divergence (Pérez-Soria, 2022).

Semi-structured interviews, focus groups, and participant observation were the instruments employed to identify perceptions regarding epistolary literature as a didactic strategy. These instruments correspond to a category pertinent to the study's purpose (Piñero et al., 2021), which guided the contributions of high school teachers and students in Pasto. The application of diverse techniques and the triangulation process reinforce the reliability of the analysis through a relationship of complementarity.

Alongside the primary category, two subcategories were identified to facilitate the understanding of perspectives on this narrative and literary typology: prior experiences with epistolary literature and interests and motivations regarding it. Three focus groups were conducted with high school students, and thirteen interviews were carried out with teachers in the fields of Humanities, Spanish Language, and Philosophy. The following diagram illustrates the structure related to the analysis category, subcategories, guiding cores, instruments applied, and participating actors.

Table 1.

Characterization of categories, subcategories, and instruments

Category	Subcategories	Guiding Cores	Instrument	Actor
Perceptions of Epistolary Literature	Prior experiences with epistolary literature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploration, approach, or reading of epistolary texts in class. • Approach, familiarity, or reading of epistolary texts outside the classroom. 	Focus Group	Students
	Interests and motivations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal and stylistic aspects found interesting in epistolary texts. 	Participant Observation	
Perceptions of Epistolary Literature	Prior experiences with epistolary literature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of epistolary literature and potential application. • Academic and didactic training in this typology. • Integration of epistolary texts in classes or activities. 	Semi-structured Interviews	Teachers
	Interests and motivations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefits. • Types of letters that elicit the greatest interest in students. • Impact on motivation toward literacy. 		

Figure No. 2. Conceptual network for the emergent category: Definitions of epistolary literature.

Source: Own elaboration (2026).

The semantic network confirms that the definitions proposed by teachers regarding epistolary literature acknowledge the existing relationship between this narrative typology and the way it establishes an interaction of realities and subjectivities between reader and author. Within this space, worldviews and configurations converge, including emotional, psychological, and contextual aspects of communication that suggest profound analytical processes (Diaz et al., 2023). The above demonstrates a comprehensive understanding of the genre, allowing it to be valued beyond its structural constraints and contemplating an interpretative richness in the emergent subcategories that facilitate its interdisciplinary linkage (Monteagudo-Robledo, 2022).

Effects of Epistolary Literature

The teachers' prior experiences with epistolary literature allow for the recognition of its beneficial effects on holistic formation processes.

Figure No. 3 Semantic Network: Effects of the use of epistolary literature.

Source: Own elaboration (2026).

The semantic network confirms the formative and emotional contribution of epistolary literature, contributing to socio-emotional development and motivation toward reading and writing (Miguez, 2024), as it transcends the student's academic plane to impact the emotional, social, and cognitive spheres (Ramos, 2022). Letters are positioned as a "safe space" for the expression of feelings and reflections on specific situations, strengthening self-knowledge, emotional healing, reconciliation, and empathy (Loera, 2022), thereby contributing to overall well-being and school coexistence.

Furthermore, it favors a contextualized understanding of literary, historical, and philosophical content, fostering proximity and sensitivity toward complex themes while promoting meaningful learning (Bracamonte, 2025). Likewise, the intimate and communicative nature of epistolary writing vindicates students' personal experiences, constituting an alternative for strengthening socio-emotional skills, as well as expressive, reflective, analytical, and argumentative abilities (Bayer, 2023).

The practice of epistolary writing strengthens the intentional use of language, which enhances narrative capacities and promotes existential, liberating, and socialization-oriented reflections (Echeverry-Fernández, 2022). However, it also requires appropriate pedagogical mediation for the proper management of sensitivity (Zakharov, 2024). Consequently, epistolary literature constitutes a valuable resource for socio-emotional education, as it encourages the exploration, recognition, and management of emotions through writing.

Similarly, epistolary literature manifests its importance in evaluation and self-evaluation processes from a personalized perspective, considering different learning rhythms and styles (Norledge, 2020) and taking into account the affective, social, and epistemological dimensions of the educational process (Bray, 2024).

Importance of Integrating Epistolary Literature into Teaching Practices

The integration of epistolary literature into didactic activities requires prior guidance from the teacher to ensure students' understanding of this narrative typology. An integrated approach allows for the consideration of different epistolary formats,

including digital ones, and active pedagogies that elicit meaningful learning.

Figure No. 4 Semantic Network: Importance of integrating epistolary literature into teaching practices.

Source: Own elaboration (2026).

The semantic network highlights the correspondence between the integration of epistolary literature and the pedagogical, curricular, and methodological spheres (Notomi, 2022). At the pedagogical level, it is necessary to rely on student-centered active pedagogies that consider their needs and interests, vindicating their literacy skills from a holistic perspective as a way of understanding and interpreting reality (Al-Shayaki, 2022). This is complemented by curricular integration, which involves considerations at the syllabus level and the incorporation of diverse disciplinary content. The digital narratives appearing in the semantic network correspond to those new digital formats through which students interact, relate, and communicate. In this regard, epistolary literature is seen to have an adaptive potential to these formats, becoming a tool that promotes and strengthens relevant and meaningful processes of learning, expression, and meaning-making (Caliskan, 2022).

Epistolary literature constitutes a path toward reclaiming meaningful, intentional, and personalized writing, vindicating the profound and symbolic value of writing as a way of "sentipensar" (sensing-thinking) education amidst the socio-cultural shifts of contemporary times (Houvenaghel & Houvenaghel, 2023). Thus, it establishes itself as a comprehensive pedagogical tool that can be included transversally within the development of school curricula (Raisinghani & Kesur, 2024).

Implementation Difficulties

The implementation of epistolary literature presents certain difficulties that pose pedagogical, methodological, and teacher-training challenges.

Figure 5 Semantic Network: Implementation difficulties.

Source: Own elaboration (2025).

Most teachers report a lack of specific training in epistolary literature; thus, the sporadic implementation of this narrative and literary typology has been conducted based on autonomous professional development. Evidence suggests that epistolary literature has not been sufficiently considered in university curricula or in continuing education processes, thereby limiting its implementation and the opportunities to strengthen pedagogical competencies (Bauman & Liotsaki, 2022). This confirms that while teacher training and self-study provide the elements necessary to integrate it into the syllabus, there is a need to further strengthen planning, learning support, and continuous guidance from other professionals, such as psychologists, due to its cognitive and socio-emotional impact (Newell, 2021).

Disinterest in reading and writing due to the use of technological media constitutes a significant difficulty, resulting in a lack of motivation toward traditional literacy (Benoit-Ríos, 2021). New forms of digital interaction and relationships limit face-to-face communication, influencing changes in the perception of writing as a form of deep expression (Pinedo-Castro, 2024). This represents a challenge for higher education and continuous training; having the support of teacher training that delves into this typology would reinforce familiarity and practice.

Another difficulty to consider involves deficiencies in student comprehension levels. Teachers state that the language employed in epistolary literature can feel distant from students' realities, hindering comprehension. This is compounded by a lack of familiarity with the genre and the codes employed (Kilby, 2020). Consequently, this demands contextualized guidance from the teacher regarding circumstantial and historical elements, as well as the challenge of updating didactic and methodological resources to ensure they are innovative and relevant to contemporary contexts (Monterrubio-Ibáñez, 2022).

Student Perceptions, Interests, and Motivations

Regarding students' recognition and prior experiences with epistolary literature, the study found a scarce conceptual understanding of the genre, reflecting a lack of familiarity with the subject (Vouillamoz, 2022). However, despite this, most students report having had some experience with this type of writing and value it as a useful medium for affective communication, self-knowledge, emotional expression, and poetic

production (Ramírez et al., 2021).

In terms of interests, they reclaim the individual and emotional expression, as well as the search for meaning and personal growth, that they perceive epistolary literature offers.

Figure 6 Themes of interest in epistolary literature for students.

Source: Own elaboration (2025).

Regarding epistolary literature, students assert its link to personal and existential interests, promoting deep reflection and the search for meaning within the thoughts and feelings it harbors (Lamata, 2020). Informative, imaginative, and creative themes generate high expectations, fostering active reflection on its utility in promoting motivation, creativity, and critical thinking from a humanistic and contemporary perspective (Benavides & Ruiz, 2022).

Students associate epistolary texts with everyday situations and emotional expression, which can be consolidated as a pillar for promoting reading and writing. This opens possibilities for strengthening learning through an approach that integrates the human, sensitive, and communicative dimensions with emerging literary and socio-cultural contexts (Arnau-Sabatés et al., 2023).

The emotive character inherent in epistolary literature and its impact on language use are noteworthy (Delgado-Villalobos & López-Riquelme, 2022). Students believe that empathy, from their role as readers, also motivates them to strengthen their vocabulary, spelling, and the application of textual structures, viewing the genre as a driver for the development of linguistic competencies (González-Rivera et al., 2023).

However, interest in this typology is conditioned by the theme; there is a marked preference for topics close to their realities, concerns, and problems. This highlights the need to address meaningful themes and orient them toward experiences of interest (Góngora-Meza & Lille-Quintal, 2023). Regarding structural elements, students highlight the narrative model of letters, their organization, and the clarity in the exposition of ideas, serving as a reference for developing narrative and discursive skills (Bravo-Andrade et al., 2021). They also recognize differences relative to other narrative typologies, valuing the relational nature of epistolary literature as a key factor in literary learning (Figueroa & Serrano, 2023).

In general, the results demonstrate that, despite conceptual ambiguity, epistolary literature sparks interest in students, especially due to its high emotional and sentimental charge. This allows for a connection between text and reader, presenting an opportunity to implement didactic strategies that deepen both the technical and affective mastery of the genre, encouraging exploration and the production of epistolary texts in the classroom (Rabal et al., 2021).

DISCUSSION

The analysis of the results reveals that epistolary literature constitutes a high-impact didactic strategy for strengthening literacy competencies and socio-emotional development in high school education. The findings confirm that, although an initial conceptual gap exists, the genre possesses an intrinsic capacity to bridge academia with student subjectivity, which can elicit free and authentic expression (Bronk-Bacon, 2024).

Despite the students' limited initial conceptual understanding of epistolary literature, there is a positive valuation of the genre. They recognize this typology as a tool for affective communication and self-knowledge. However, its success requires active pedagogies and pedagogical mediation that integrates both the socio-emotional dimension and the linguistic components present in the texts. Such mediation should strengthen communicative skills grounded in trust (Bingham & Gerde, 2023).

By contrasting the contributions of teachers and students, it is found that despite the benefits of epistolary literature in socio-emotional reinforcement and literacy motivation, significant implementation challenges remain. These challenges necessitate addressing barriers in teacher training, presenting an opportunity for university curricula to include this literary typology from a contextualized didactic perspective. It is essential that, within the classroom and through teacher guidance, clear guidelines are provided to bolster students' confidence in the processes of epistolary reading and writing (Delgado-Villalobos & López-Riquelme, 2022).

The influence of digital formats on younger generations suggests the need to adapt formats and methodologies, considering the new digital narratives through which students communicate and interact (Sangacha Aroca et al., 2025).

CONCLUSIONS

The study concludes that epistolary literature is a pedagogical tool that contributes significantly to the strengthening of literacy competencies. These competencies impact not only students' cognitive development but also the socio-emotional skills found in self-knowledge, empathy, and resilience.

A relationship of complementarity is recognized between the emotional weight of epistolary texts and the motivation toward sensitive reading. However, appropriate didactic guidance is required to ensure that comprehension is contextualized, ultimately leading to the development of linguistic, narrative, and socio-emotional competencies.

Both teachers and students recognize the beneficial effects of epistolary literature. Educators regard it as a pedagogical tool that fosters situated, contextualized, and meaningful learning across various domains of holistic formation. Students, in turn, value it as a medium to articulate their thoughts with greater depth.

At the pedagogical level, difficulties were identified regarding teacher training in epistolary literature. This suggests the need for its integration into higher education curricula to highlight its epistemological, curricular, and didactic contributions.

One of the most significant challenges in implementing epistolary literature as a didactic strategy lies in its adaptability to digital formats and gamification, supported by active

pedagogies.

The diversity of themes, contexts, and styles present in epistolary texts favors their pedagogical incorporation from an interdisciplinary perspective, which ultimately enhances the holistic formation of the student.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the development or disclosure of the research results.

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